

Title Of the Document	Internal Metadata Fields ODISSEI Portal					
Description	<p>The spreadsheet contains the list of the metadata fields that are currently supported in the ODISSEI Portal. Each sheet refers to a Metadata block in the ODISSEI portal.</p> <p>This document can be used by metadata providers to assess whether they are able to provide all the mandatory information and to create mappings from the metadata schema in use by the provider to the one used by the ODISSEI Portal.</p>					
Authors	Angelica Maineri (ODISSEI) & Ricarda Braukmann (DANS)					
Last updated	12-05-2023					
Please contact fairsupport@odissei-data.nl in case of questions						
Table of content						
Citation Metadata	<i>Refers to a metadata block where basic metadata of the dataset is stored (i.e. author, description, contributors etc.)</i>					
Social Science and Humanities Metadata	<i>Refers to a metadata block where domain-specific metadata is stored (i.e. references to unit of analysis, universe etc.). This metadata fields are based on DDI.</i>					
Variable Information	<i>Refers to a metadata block where information about variables can be stored</i>					
Question Information	<i>Refers to a metadata block where information about questions can be stored</i>					
Explanation columns						
Fieldlabel	Here the name of the field visible in the User Interface is displayed					
name	Here the name of the field used in the system is displayed					
description	Here the description of the field is given					
Mandatory	If a block contains Mandatory fields, this indicated in this column by color coding					
Recommended	If a block contains Recommended fields, this indicated in this column by color coding					
Note that subfields are in lower case letters and non-bold while the parent field is printed larger and in bold						

FieldLabel	SystemName	Description	Mandatory	Recommended
Dataset Persistent ID	datasetPersistentId	The Persistent Identifier of the Dataset		
Publication Date	distributionDate	The date on which the dataset was published in the source repository		
License/Data Use Agreement	license	The license or agreement that is attached to the dataset to describe if and how it can be re-used		
Title	title	The main title of the Dataset		
Subtitle	subtitle	A secondary title that amplifies or states certain limitations on the Dataset		
Alternative Title	alternativeTitle	Either 1) a title commonly used to refer to the Dataset or 2) an alternative title		
Alternative URL	alternativeURL	Another URL where one can view or access the data in the Dataset		
Other Identifier	otherId	Another unique identifier for the Dataset (e.g. producer's or another identifier)		
Agency Identifier	otherIdAgency	The name of the agency that generated the other identifier		
Identifier	otherIdValue	Another identifier uniquely identifies the Dataset		
Author	author	The entity, e.g. a person or organization, that created the Dataset		
Name	authorName	The name of the author, such as the person's name or the name of an organization		
Affiliation	authorAffiliation	The name of the entity affiliated with the author, e.g. an organization's name		
Identifier Type	authorIdentifier	The type of identifier that uniquely identifies the author (e.g. ORCID, ISNI)		
Identifier	authorIdentifierScheme	Uniquely identifies the author when paired with an identifier type		
Point of Contact	datasetContact	We require a general email address for the datasets associated with the Dataset		
Name	datasetContactName	The name of the point of contact, e.g. the person's name or the name of an organization		
Affiliation	datasetContactAffiliation	The name of the entity affiliated with the point of contact, e.g. an organization's name		
E-mail	datasetContactEmail	The point of contact's email address		
Description	dsDescription	A summary describing the purpose, nature, and scope of the Dataset		
Text	dsDescriptionValue	A summary describing the purpose, nature, and scope of the Dataset		
Date	dsDescriptionDate	The date when the description was added to the Dataset. If the Dataset contains multiple descriptions, the date of the most recent description is used.		
Subject	subject	The area of study relevant to the Dataset		
Keyword	keyword	A key term that describes an important aspect of the Dataset and its content		
Term	keywordValue	A key term that describes important aspects of the Dataset		
Controlled Vocabulary Name	keywordVocabulary	The controlled vocabulary used for the keyword term (e.g. LCSH, MeSH)		
Controlled Vocabulary URL	keywordVocabularyURI	The URL where one can access information about the term's controlled vocabulary		
Topic Classification	topicClassValue	Indicates a broad, important topic or subject that the Dataset covers		
Term	topicClassValue	A topic or subject term		
Controlled Vocabulary Name	topicClassVocab	The controlled vocabulary used for the keyword term (e.g. LCSH, MeSH)		
Controlled Vocabulary URL	topicClassVocabURI	The URL where one can access information about the term's controlled vocabulary		
Related Publication	publication	The article or report that uses the data in the Dataset. The full list of related publications is available in the Related Publications field.		
Citation	publicationCitation	The full bibliographic citation for the related publication		
Identifier Type	publicationIDType	The type of identifier that uniquely identifies a related publication		
Identifier	publicationIDNumber	The identifier for a related publication		
URL	publicationURL	The URL form of the identifier entered in the Identifier field, e.g. the DOI URL if applicable		
Notes	notesText	Additional information about the Dataset		
Language	language	A language that the Dataset's files is written in		

Producer	producer	The entity, such a person or organization, managing the finance:
Name	producerName	The name of the entity, e.g. the person's name or the name of an organization
Affiliation	producerAffiliation	The name of the entity affiliated with the producer, e.g. an organization's name
Abbreviated Name	producerAbbreviation	The producer's abbreviated name (e.g. IQSS, ICPSR)
URL	producerURL	The URL of the producer's website
Logo URL	producerLogoURL	The URL of the producer's logo
Production Date	productionDate	The date when the data were produced (not distributed, published)
Production Location	productionPlace	The location where the data and any related materials were produced
Contributor	contributor	The entity, such as a person or organization, responsible for collecting the data
Type	contributorType	Indicates the type of contribution made to the dataset
Name	contributorName	The name of the contributor, e.g. the person's name or the name of an organization
Funding Information	grantNumber	Information about the Dataset's financial support
Agency	grantNumberValue	The agency that provided financial support for the Dataset
Identifier	grantNumberAgency	The grant identifier or contract identifier of the agency that provided financial support
Distributor	distributor	The entity, such as a person or organization, designated to generate the Dataset
Name	distributorName	The name of the entity, e.g. the person's name or the name of an organization
Affiliation	distributorAffiliation	The name of the entity affiliated with the distributor, e.g. an organization's name
Abbreviated Name	distributorAbbreviation	The distributor's abbreviated name (e.g. IQSS, ICPSR)
URL	distributorURL	The URL of the distributor's webpage
Logo URL	distributorLogoURL	The URL of the distributor's logo image, used to show the image on the Dataset's page
Distribution Date	distributionDate	The date when the Dataset was made available for distribution/publishing
Depositor	depositor	The entity, such as a person or organization, that deposited the Dataset
Deposit Date	dateOfDeposit	The date when the Dataset was deposited into the repository
Time Period	timePeriodCovered	The time period that the data refer to. Also known as span. This period may be different from the distribution date.
Start Date	timePeriodCoveredStart	The start date of the time period that the data refer to
End Date	timePeriodCoveredEnd	The end date of the time period that the data refer to
Date of Collection	dateOfCollection	The dates when the data were collected or generated
Start Date	dateOfCollectionStart	The date when the data collection started
End Date	dateOfCollectionEnd	The date when the data collection ended
Data Type	kindOfData	The type of data included in the files (e.g. survey data, clinical data)
Series	series	Information about the dataset series to which the Dataset belongs
Name	seriesName	The name of the dataset series
Information	seriesInformation	Can include 1) a history of the series and 2) a summary of features that apply to the series
Software	software	Information about the software used to generate the Dataset
Name	softwareName	The name of software used to generate the Dataset
Version	softwareVersion	The version of the software used to generate the Dataset, e.g. 4.11
Related Material	relatedMaterial	Information, such as a persistent ID or citation, about the material related to the Dataset
Related Dataset	relatedDatasets	Information, such as a persistent ID or citation, about a related Dataset
Other Reference	otherReferences	Information, such as a persistent ID or citation, about another type of related material

Data Source	dataSources	Information, such as a persistent ID or citation, about sources of
Origin of Historical Sources	originOfSources	For historical sources, the origin and any rules followed in establ
Characteristic of Sources	characteristicOfSour	Characteristics not already noted elsewhere
Documentation and Access to	accessToSources	1) Methods or procedures for accessing data sources and 2) any

Field Label	System Name	Description	Recommended
Unit of Analysis	unitOfAnalysis	Basic unit of analysis or observation that this Dataset describes, such as individuals, families/households, etc.	
Universe	universe	Description of the population covered by the data in the file; the group of people or other elements that are included in the data.	
Time Method	timeMethod	The time method or time dimension of the data collection, such as panel, cross-sectional, trend, or retrospective.	
Data Collector	dataCollector	Individual, agency or organization responsible for administering the questionnaire or interview.	
Collector Training	collectorTraining	Type of training provided to the data collector.	
Frequency	frequencyOfDataCollection	If the data collected includes more than one point in time, indicate the frequency with which the data are collected.	
Sampling Procedure	samplingProcedure	Type of sample and sample design used to select the survey respondents to represent the population.	
Target Sample Size	targetSampleSize	Specific information regarding the target sample size, actual sample size, and the formula used to determine the sample size.	
Actual Size	targetSampleActualSize	Actual sample size.	
Formula	targetSampleSizeFormula	Sample size formula.	
Major Deviations for Sample Design	deviationsFromSampleDesign	Show correspondence as well as discrepancies between the sampled units (obtained) and available units.	
Collection Mode	collectionMode	Method used to collect the data; instrumentation characteristics (e.g., telephone interview, mail survey, etc.).	
Type of Research Instrument	researchInstrument	Type of data collection instrument used. Structured indicates an instrument in which all responses are predetermined.	
Characteristics of Data Collection	dataCollectionSituation	Description of noteworthy aspects of the data collection situation. Includes information on factors that may affect the quality of the data.	
Actions to Minimize Losses	actionsToMinimizeLosses	Summary of actions taken to minimize data loss. Include information on actions such as follow-up, nonresponse, etc.	
Control Operations	controlOperations	Methods to facilitate data control performed by the primary investigator or by the data archive.	
Weighting	weighting	The use of sampling procedures might make it necessary to apply weights to produce accurate estimates.	
Cleaning Operations	cleaningOperations	Methods used to clean the data collection, such as consistency checking, wildcode checking, or other data cleaning procedures.	
Study Level Error Notes	datasetLevelErrorNotes	Note element used for any information annotating or clarifying the methodology and processing of the data.	
Response Rate	responseRate	Percentage of sample members who provided information.	
Estimates of Sampling Error	samplingErrorEstimate	Measure of how precisely one can estimate a population value from a given sample.	
Other Forms of Data Appraisal	otherDataAppraisal	Other issues pertaining to the data appraisal. Describe issues such as response variance, nonresponse, etc.	
Notes	socialScienceNotes	Notes about this Dataset.	
Type	socialScienceNotesType	Type of note.	
Subject	socialScienceNotesSubject	Note subject.	
Text	socialScienceNotesText	Text for this note.	

Field Label	System Name	Description	Recommended
Variable	variable	This element describes all of the features of a single (conceptual)variable in a soc	
Conceptual Variable Name	conceptVariableName	Name of the conceptual variable.	
Conceptual Variable Definition	conceptVariableDefinition	The definition of the conceptual variable.	
Conceptual Variable ID	conceptVariableID	The ID of the conceptual variable.	
Conceptual Variable Object Type	conceptVariableObjecttype	The related object type for the conceptual variable.	
Conceptual Variable Valid from	conceptVariableValidFrom	Valid from date provided by the metadata distributor.	
Conceptual Variable Version	conceptVariableVersion	Version number of the conceptual variable provided by the metadata distributor.	
Conceptual Variable Version Responsibility	conceptVariableVersionResponsib	Person or organization responsible for the version change.	
Variabelengroepnaam	conceptVariableGroepnaam	Variabelengroepnaam (specific field mentioned in CBS metadata)	
Thema	conceptVariableThema	Thema (specific field mentioned in CBS metadata)	
Waardestelselnaam	conceptVariableWaardestelselnaam	Waardestelselnaam (specific field mentioned in CBS metadata)	
Variable ID	variableId	Id to uniquely identify the variable.	
Variable Name	variableName	Name of the variable.	
Variable Label	variableLabel	Short description of the variable.	
Variable Vocabulary URI	variableVocabularyURI	Vocabulary URI for the variable.	
Variabele Definition	variableDefinition	Extra information related to the definition of the variable.	
Variabele Processing Instruction	variableProcessingInstruction	Information about how the variable was processed.	
Variable Data Type	variableDataType	Data type of the variable.	
Volgnummer	variableVolgnummer	Volgnummer (specific field mentioned in CBS metadata)	
Trefwoord	variableTrefwoord	Trefwoord (specific field mentioned in CBS metadata)	

Field Label	SystemName	Description
Question Scheme Name	questionSchemeName	The name of the questionnaire used.
Question Scheme Description	questionSchemeDescription	A short description of the questionnaire used.
Question	question	This field contains all information about a single question from the
Question ID	questionId	Identifier for the question.
Question Name	questionName	Name of the question.
Question Text	questionText	The literal question as stated in the questionnaire.